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Time Series Analysis of Malaria Cases at Redeemer's University Health Centre (2014–2022)

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ABSTRACT

Planning for public health effectively requires an awareness of the temporal dynamics of malaria, which continues to be a major worldwide health concern. The study aimed at analysing the trend of malaria cases by investigating the factors associated with these cases, also to forecast future occurrences in Redeemer's University. The time series data was modelled using the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) approach. The parameters for the ARIMA model were selected through the Box-Jenkins method, a systematic technique for identifying the optimal model parameters. Analysis showed a seasonal pattern in malaria cases, rainfall emerged as the most important factor with a strong statistical association indicating that higher rainfall levels lead to increased malaria incidence. The dry season also significantly influenced malaria cases, although its impact was less pronounced compared to rainfall. The result of this study predicted that there will be a downward trend of malaria cases in Redeemer's University for the next five years (2023 – 2027). This study recommended that Redeemer's University should provide more preventive measures and effective intervention strategies such as vaccines, mosquito nets, insecticides to control malaria fever.

Keywords: Climatic, forecasting, trend, treatment, patient, time series

1. INTRODUCTION

Malaria continues to be a persistent global health concern, especially in areas where the climate favors the spread of the Plasmodium parasite by mosquito (Mohammadkhani et al., 2016; Mafwele & Lee, 2022). The disease poses a serious threat to public health despite major attempts to control it, particularly in prevalent areas. According to Talapko et al., (2019), malaria is a serious illness brought on by parasites belonging to the genus Plasmodium, humans contract the disease by the bite of a female Anopheles mosquito carrying the infection. It has been revealed that malaria remains the leading cause of death worldwide, underlining the importance of early detection and timely treatment to prevent adverse outcomes (Guinovart et al., 2006; Gelband et al., 2020).

Despite over a century of international efforts and research to improve malaria prevention, diagnosis, and treatment, the disease continues to cause significant illness and mortality (Bates & Herrington, 2007). Malaria is the most prevalent disease in Africa and certain Asian countries, where it has the highest number of native cases (Kumar et al., 2012).

Malaria took the lives of 435,000 people and affected an estimated 219 million people in 2017. Around 249 million cases had been documented worldwide by 2022, and 608,000 people had died in 85 different nations (Kogan, 2020). The WHO African Region is responsible for 94% of cases (233 million) and 95% of fatalities (580,000) worldwide in 2022, representing a disproportionately high burden of malaria. Notably, children under the age of five accounted for roughly 80% of all malaria-related deaths in the Region.

A time series comprises of sequentially recorded observations through time (Adhikari & Agrawal, 2013). A time series is a collection of observations made at regular or irregular intervals that measure a particular quantity of interest. It is possible to document the observations on a daily, weekly, quarterly, annual, or bi-annual basis (Broomhead & Jones, 1989).

1. 1. Time series analysis of malaria cases

In a study by Nwakuwa (2020), a time series analysis was conducted on the incidence rates of malaria and typhoid fever. Least Square Estimation was employed to determine the trend of both diseases, revealing a gradual downward trend for both. ARIMA modeling was utilized to characterize the overall behavior and occurrence patterns of both diseases throughout the study period, with forecasts of future occurrences generated. The findings indicated that the occurrence of both illnesses is affected by seasonal factors.

Adewole et al., (2023) conducted a research study that investigated the trend and seasonality of malaria fever in Ogun State, Nigeria over the period 2016-2021 and also predicted its prevalence in the year 2023. The study used secondary data obtained from the World Development Indicators, the data was pre-processed to ensure that it was in the appropriate format for time series analysis. The methodology included data collection, preprocessing, time series visualization, stationary testing, time series decomposition, modeling, model evaluation and forecasting.

A study was also conducted by Adekola et al., (2023) to evaluate the occurrence of malaria in peri-urban regions, a time-series analysis was undertaken on 1,141 individuals suspected of febrile illness who visited a peri-urban health center over a year-long period (February 2020 – January 2021). Every individual who sought treatment at the hospital and underwent malaria testing was included in the study.

The findings from the 12-month study revealed an overall malaria prevalence of 24% ($p < 0.05$). The study's conclusion emphasized that malaria continues to be a notable public health matter in the country, particularly in regions conducive to mosquito vector breeding. Consequently, efforts to eliminate malaria should be intensified to protect individuals, especially those in vulnerable areas. Anwar et al., (2016) performed a time series examination of malaria in Afghanistan, employing ARIMA models to forecast future incidence patterns. Also in 2014, Aregawi et al., (2014) conducted a time series analysis examining the trends in malaria cases and deaths in hospitals, as well as the impact of antimalarial interventions in Ethiopia from 2001 - 2011.

Ogbuagada (2022) conducted a study centered on a multivariate time series model analyzing malaria cases among inhabitants in the Jimeta metropolis of Adamawa State. The study utilized the vector autoregressive (VAR) model for modeling purposes. A descriptive analysis of the data was carried out. The selection of the lag order for the stationary VAR model indicated a lag of three as the optimal choice for the VAR model with malaria cases among children, adults, and pregnant women. The forecasts indicated that the malaria case rates are highest among adults, followed by children, and then pregnant women.

Ostovar et al. (2016) aimed to create a malaria forecast model for malaria-endemic regions in southeastern Iran, by incorporating both climatic variables and historical malaria illness data. Using univariate auto-regressive integrated moving average or transfer function models, noteworthy forecasters from the climatic variables were identified to forecast the monthly and weekly malaria cases. The study concluded that time-series models can effectively predict malaria incidence with reasonable accuracy, thus serving as a valuable component of a malaria early-warning system. However, the feasibility of employing routine climatic data in statistical models is found to be significantly limited.

In their study, Wangdi et al. (2010) sought to create forecasting and prediction models for malaria incidence in districts where malaria is prevalent in Bhutan. They employed time series analysis and ARIMAX, examining monthly malaria cases from 1994 to 2008 across seven malaria-prevalent districts. Multiplicative seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models were employed to identify the best model using data from 1994 to 2006. Subsequently, the most suitable fit model for each individual district and the overall prevalent area was developed, and monthly cases from January to December 2009 and 2010 were predicted.

The ARIMA models derived from time-series analysis proved effective in predicting the number of cases in Bhutan's endemic areas. However, there was variability in the predictors of malaria cases when employing the ARIMAX model with selected lag times and climatic predictors. Nevertheless, the ARIMA forecasting models can be valuable for planning and managing malaria prevention and control programs in Bhutan.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

Redeemer's University, located in Ede, Osun State, was founded by the Redeemed Christian Church of God in 2005. In 2013, the university secured a World Bank Grant to establish the African Centre of Excellence for Genomics of Infectious Diseases (ACEGID). Redeemer's University won this grant after competing with 15 prestigious universities from

West and Central Africa. The rigorous evaluation process and the high quality of the university's proposal led to the award and the creation of the center.

2. 2. Data Collection

The data for this project was obtained from the Redeemer’s University Health center. The data is on patients treated for malaria for 8 years (i.e., from January 2014 to December 2022). For the dependent variable, malaria is the outcome of interest. The independent variables include the age of patient (<5 years, >5 years), gender, treatment method (tablet only, injection only, tablet and injection), admission status (in-patient or out-patient), season (rainy or dry season). The data collected was entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 20)

2. 3. Demographic analysis of patient

Table 1 shows that 3393 (7.26%) patients had malaria in 2014, 3444 (7.37%) in 2015, 3283 (7.03%) in 2016, 3809 (8.15%) in 2017, 5081 (10.87%) in 2018, 5766 (12.33%) in 2019, 4402 (9.42%) in 2020, 7424 (15.89%) in 2021 and 10124 (21.67%) in 2022. This implies that 2022 had the highest rate of malaria cases from 2014 to 2022. Therefore, the incidence of malaria has significantly increased over this period, peaking in 2022.

Table 1. Year 2014 – 2022.

YEAR	Frequency	Percent
2014	3393	7.26
2015	3444	7.37
2016	3283	7.03
2017	3809	8.15
2018	5081	10.87
2019	5766	12.34
2020	4402	9.42
2021	7424	15.89
2022	10124	21.67
TOTAL	46726	100

Table 2 shows the admission status of the patients. It shows that 3122 (6.68%) patients were admitted while 43604 (93.32%) were not admitted. This implies that majority of the patients were out-patients.

Table 2. Admission Status.

	Frequency	Percent
IN PATIENT	3122	6.68
OUT PATIENT	43604	93.32
TOTAL	46726	100

Table 3 shows the age of the patients who were treated for malaria. From this table 1638 (3.51%) in the age group <5 years and 45088 (96.49%) in the age group >5 years. This implies that the majority of patients who were treated for malaria fall in the age group >5 years.

Table 3. Patients Age (years).

	Frequency	Percent
<5 Years	1638	3.51
>5 Years	45088	96.49
TOTAL	46726	100

Table 4 shows the mode of treatments for patients treated for malaria. From this table, 42678 (66.93%) patients were treated with tablet only, 4048 (6.35%) were treated with injection only, 17043 (26.73%) were treated with both tablet and injection. This implies that majority of the malaria patients were treated with tablet only.

Table 4. Mode of Treatment.

	Frequency	Percent
Tablet only	42678	66.93
Injection only	4048	6.35
Tablet and Injection	17043	26.73
TOTAL	63769	100

Table 5 shows the gender of the patients who were treated for malaria. 24268 (51.94%) were female patients while 22458 (48.06%) were male patients. The majority of the patients were females.

Table 5. Gender of Patient.

	Frequency	Percent
Female	24268	51.94
Male	22458	48.06
TOTAL	46726	100

Table 6 shows the season (i.e., rainy or dry season), 29462 (63.05%) patients were treated during the rainy season while 17264 (36.95%) were treated during dry season. This aligns with the study by Oguntade et al (2020), which stated that more malaria cases were recorded in rainy season than dry season.

Table 6. Season.

	Frequency	Percent
Rainy season	29462	63.05
Dry season	17264	36.95
TOTAL	46726	100

2. 4. Time series plot

Figure 1. Monthly malaria cases from January 2014 to December 2022.

The time series plot in Figure 1 shows an upward increase in the malaria cases trend in Redeemer’s University Health Center. The series shows a seasonal pattern where the incidence of malaria cases spiked in May 2022.

From Figure 2, an upward increase in the trend of malaria cases during both raining and dry season is seen. During raining season there is a more upward increase in malaria cases from 2020, this means that malaria cases in the Redeemer’s University Health Center are greatly affected by raining season more than dry season. This is because heavy rainfall provides good breeding conditions for the mosquitoes.

Figure 2. Trend of climatic change.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Cross - tabulation

3. 1. 1. Hypothesis testing for significant impact of rainfall on incidence of malaria cases

Null Hypothesis (H_0): Rainfall has no significant impact on the incidence of malaria cases.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): Rainfall has a significant impact on the incidence of malaria cases.

From Table 7, R square appears to be 0.935 which indicates that 93.5% of the variance in the incidence of malaria cases can be explained by rainfall.

The results from the ANOVA Table 8 shows that the regression model is significant ($F = 100.416, p < 0.01$). The F-value appears to be high which indicates a strong relationship between rainfall and the incidence of malaria cases.

Table 7. Regression Analysis of rainfall against the incidence of malaria cases: Model summary.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.967 ^a	.935	.926	626.20299
a. Predictors: (Constant), Raining season				

Table 8. Regression Analysis of rainfall against the incidence of malaria cases: ANOVA.

ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	39376308.286	1	39376308.286	100.416	.000 ^b
	Residual	2744911.270	7	392130.181		
	Total	42121219.556	8			
a. Dependent Variable: Malaria cases						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Raining season						

From the coefficients Table 9, the results indicates that for every one unit increase in rainfall, the incidence of malaria cases increases by 1.232 units. The p-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that rainfall has a significant impact on the incidence of malaria cases.

Table 9. Regression Analysis of rainfall against the incidence of malaria cases: Coefficients.

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1158.837	453.367		2.556	.038
	Raining season	1.232	.123	.967	10.021	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Malaria cases						

The tables above show the results of the regression analysis investigating the impact of rainfall on the incidence of malaria cases.

3. 1. 2. Hypothesis testing for significant impact of dry season on the incidence of malaria cases

Null Hypothesis (H_0): Dry season has no significant impact on the incidence of malaria cases.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): Dry season has a significant impact on the incidence of malaria cases.

From the model summary Table 10, R square appears to be 0.592 which indicates that 59.2% of the variance in the incidence of malaria cases can be explained by dry season.

Table 10. Regression Analysis of dry season against the incidence of malaria cases: Model Summary.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.769 ^a	.592	.533	1567.39097
a. Predictors: (Constant), Dry season				

The results from the ANOVA Table 11 shows that the regression model is significant ($F = 10.145, p < 0.05$). The F-value indicates a weak relationship between dry season and the incidence of malaria cases.

Table 11. Regression Analysis of dry season against the incidence of malaria cases: ANOVA.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24924218.303	1	24924218.303	10.145	.015 ^b
	Residual	17197001.253	7	2456714.465		
	Total	42121219.556	8			
a. Dependent Variable: Malaria cases						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Dry season						

From the coefficients Table 12, the results indicates that for every one unit increase in dry season, the incidence of malaria cases increases by 2.453 units. The p-value is 0.015 which is less than 0.05 is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that dry season has a significant impact on the incidence of malaria cases.

Table 12. Regression Analysis of dry season against the incidence of malaria cases: Coefficients.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	485.727	1567.141		.310	.766
	Dry season	2.453	.770	.769	3.185	.015

a. Dependent Variable: Malaria cases

The tables above show the results of the regression analysis investigating the impact of dry season on the incidence of malaria cases.

3. 2. Test for stationarity

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is a statistical test to determine if a given time series is stationary or not.

Null Hypothesis: The time series is non-stationary and has a unit root.

Alternative Hypothesis: The time series is stationary and does not have a unit root.

Table 13. ADF Test for Malaria.

Null Hypothesis: Malaria has a unit root				
Exogenous: Constant				
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag = 12)				
			t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic			-5.015906	0.0001
Test critical values:	1% level		-3.492523	
	5% level		-2.888669	
	10% level		-2.581313	
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.

Malaria (-1)	-0.386232	0.077001	-5.015906	0.0000
C	168.2399	42.69386	3.940611	0.0001
R-squared	0.193296	Mean dependent var		0.149533
Adjusted R-squared	0.185613	S.D. dependent var		303.2126
S.E. of regression	273.6293	Akaike info criterion		14.07994
Sum squared resid	7861664.	Schwarz criterion		14.12990
Log likelihood	-751.2768	Hannan-Quinn criter.		14.10019
F-statistic	25.15931	Durbin-Watson stat		1.723382
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000002			

Since the p-value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the time series does not have a unit root and is stationary.

Model Description

Table 14. Model Description.

Model Description			
			Model Type
Model ID	Malaria cases	Model_1	ARIMA (0,0,1) (1,0,0)

3. 3. Diagnostic Checking

The Ljung Box test is used to evaluate the adequacy of a time series model.

H_0 : There is no significant autocorrelation in the time series.

H_1 : There is significant autocorrelation in the time series.

The p-value (0.348) as seen in Table 15, is greater than 0.05 which indicates that the model is adequate for forecasting purposes. Therefore, we do not reject the null hypothesis and we conclude that there is no significant autocorrelation.

Table 15. The Ljung Box test.

Model Statistics													
Model	Number of Predictors	Model Fit statistics								Ljung-Box Q (18)			Number of Outliers
		Stationary R-square	R-squared	RMSE	MAPE	MAE	MaxAPE	MaxAE	Normalized BIC	Statistics	DF	Sig.	
Malaria cases-Model_1	0	.413	.423	264.165	54.377	166.891	659.106	1407.839	11.283	17.602	16	.348	0

3. 4. Forecast values

Table 16. Forecast Values for 2023.

Forecast													
Model		Jan 2023	Feb 2023	Mar 2023	Apr 2023	May 2023	Jun 2023	Jul 2023	Aug 2023	Sep 2023	Oct 2023	Nov 2023	Dec 2023
DIFF(DATA, 1)-Model_1	Forecast	291	576	568	517	786	932	997	462	328	416	562	285
	UCL	718	1537	1515	1379	2098	2486	2661	1233	876	1111	1499	762
	LCL	90	154	152	138	211	249	267	124	88	111	150	76

Table 17. Forecast Values for 2024.

Forecast													
Model		Jan 2024	Feb 2024	Mar 2024	Apr 2024	May 2024	Jun 2024	Jul 2024	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024
DIFF(DATA, 1)-Model_1	Forecast	366	498	495	473	575	623	643	449	384	428	492	359
	UCL	1044	1442	1432	1371	1666	1803	1861	1301	1111	1240	1425	1040
	LCL	86	114	114	109	132	143	147	103	88	98	113	82

Table 18. Forecast Values for 2025.

Forecast													
Model		Jan 2025	Feb 2025	Mar 2025	Apr 2025	May 2025	Jun 2025	Jul 2025	Aug 2025	Sep 2025	Oct 2025	Nov 2025	Dec 2025
DIFF(DATA, 1)-Model_1	Forecast	400	461	460	450	493	512	519	440	408	430	459	396
	UCL	1174	1357	1353	1326	1451	1506	1528	1294	1202	1265	1350	1166
	LCL	89	103	102	100	110	114	115	98	91	96	102	88

Table 19. Forecast Values for 2026.

Forecast													
Model		Jan 2026	Feb 2026	Mar 2026	Apr 2026	May 2026	Jun 2026	Jul 2026	Aug 2026	Sep 2026	Oct 2026	Nov 2026	Dec 2026
DIFF(DATA, 1)-Model_1	Forecast	416	444	443	439	458	466	469	434	420	430	443	414
	UCL	1228	1312	1310	1297	1353	1376	1386	1283	1240	1270	1308	1222
	LCL	92	98	98	97	101	103	104	96	93	95	98	91

Table 20. Forecast Values for 2027.

Forecast													
Model		Jan 2027	Feb 2027	Mar 2027	Apr 2027	May 2027	Jun 2027	Jul 2027	Aug 2027	Sep 2027	Oct 2027	Nov 2027	Dec 2027
DIFF(DATA, 1)-Model_1	Forecast	423	436	436	434	443	446	448	432	425	430	436	422
	UCL	1251	1289	1288	1283	1308	1318	1323	1276	1256	1270	1288	1248
	LCL	93	96	96	96	98	98	99	95	94	95	96	93

3. 5. Forecast charts

Figure 3 shows a five-year forecast for malaria cases. Based on this, we have a downward continuous trend.

A total of 46,726 cases of malaria were analyzed. Table 1 – 6 shows the demographic analysis of the cases, explaining that more patients were treated for malaria in May 2022. The

analysis revealed an overall trend in the number of malaria cases over the study period. There was a noticeable fluctuation in the annual number of cases, with certain years showing spikes that may correspond to specific events.

Figure 3. Five-year forecast chart for malaria cases.

One of the findings from the time series analysis was the seasonal pattern in malaria cases. The data showed a clear increase in the number of malaria cases during the rainy season compared to the dry season.

From the regression analysis tables, a p-value less than 0.05 shows that the results were significant. For rainy season, the F-value appeared to be high which indicates a strong relationship between rainfall and the incidence of malaria cases, this finding aligns with existing literature, which often links increased rainfall with higher mosquito breeding sites, thus increasing the risk of malaria transmission (Smith et al., 2004). For dry season, The F-value was low which indicates a weak relationship between dry season and the incidence of malaria cases. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was employed to determine the stationarity of the malaria time series, with a t-statistic of -5.015906 and a p-value of 0.0001, the null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that the time series is stationary. The Ljung-Box test was used to evaluate the adequacy of the ARIMA (0,0,1) (1,0,0) model for forecasting malaria cases. With a p-value of 0.348, null hypothesis was not rejected, this indicates that the model is adequate and there is no significant autocorrelation in the residuals, making the model suitable for forecasting purposes.

The ARIMA model forecasted malaria cases for the years 2023 to 2027, providing point forecasts along with upper and lower confidence limits. The confidence intervals provide a range within which the true values are expected to fall, offering a measure of uncertainty around the point forecasts. For example, the forecast for January 2023 is 291 cases, with an upper confidence limit (UCL) of 718 and a lower confidence limit (LCL) of 90. This range indicates the potential variability in the forecasted values, accounting for the inherent uncertainty in

predictions. The forecasts for subsequent years show a similar pattern, with a general decrease in the number of malaria cases and narrowing confidence intervals, suggesting increased precision over time.

4. CONCLUSION

This study considered factors related to malaria fever incidence in Redeemer's University health center. It showed a seasonal pattern in the trend of malaria cases and rainfall emerged as the most important factor with a strong statistical association indicating that higher rainfall levels lead to increased malaria incidence. The dry season also significantly influenced malaria cases, although its impact was less pronounced compared to rainfall. The five-year forecast shows downward trend, generally the rate will vary from month to month as cases may likely increase every month from January to December. Based on the data supply from Redeemer's University, there may be a need to pay more attention to population greater than 5 years for malaria intervention and control programs.

To reduce the occurrence of malaria in Redeemer's University, systems should be established for continuous monitoring of climate and environmental factors, such as rainfall patterns and temperature variations, which influence malaria transmission. Public health education campaigns should be conducted throughout the year, focusing on preventive measures such as the use of bed nets, early diagnosis, and timely treatment.

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